

REVIEWING THE SUSTAINABILITY TRACKING PROCESS FOR CROSS-UNIVERSITY CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER

PROJECT REPORT 2025

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1. PREAMBLE

To reference this report:

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The University of Manchester (UoM) Estates team has a strong ambition to advance sustainable processes and workflows across its construction projects. Central to this effort is the EPM PM7 sustainability tracker, a document that sets out sustainability indicators for each stage of a project and requires suppliers and contractors to provide evidence of sustainable practices. This tool, first introduced in 2015, has supported traceability and accountability in delivering sustainability outcomes. However, after nearly a decade in operation, it no longer fully reflects current sustainability priorities, evolving frameworks, or the university's ambitious zero-carbon transition goals.

With UoM investing £150 million in decarbonising all university buildings and pursuing projects such as energy efficiency upgrades, improved glazing, and low-carbon heating systems, there is a timely need to update the EPM PM7 process and tracker. The project was established to deliver this update, drawing on academic expertise in sustainable construction, knowledge of frameworks such as BREEAM, and experience in retrofit green infrastructure. It also seeks to integrate perspectives from a broad range of stakeholders, including academic staff, technical teams, end users, and external suppliers, to ensure the revised tracker is both innovative and practical.

The intended impact is to raise the level of integration of sustainability into UoM's construction processes through measurable indicators and robust data. By examining state-of-the-art literature and practices and a workshop with relevant stakeholders, the project generated recommendations aligned with the long-term direction of refurbishment at the university. Beyond its immediate outputs, the initiative aims to establish a precedent for inclusive and evidence-based process improvement, offering a model that can be adapted to other organisational procedures across UoM.

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2. METHODOLOGY

The project adopted a two-step approach: a systematic literature review (SLR), followed by a co-development workshop with key stakeholders. The SLR aimed to identify key insights, best practices, and gaps in sustainability tracking processes, indicators, and workflows that could inform the update of the EPM PM7 tracker. Building on these findings, the workshop provided a collaborative forum to evaluate and suggest improvements to the UoM sustainability tracking process for both new construction and retrofitting projects.

Figure 1: RoundView Learning tool to provoke new thinking, used in networking at start.

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3. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW PROCESS

The SLR followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Figure 2). A comprehensive search was performed in the Scopus databases, covering publications up to February 2025. To ensure relevance to updating the tracker, the search strategy was structured around three thematic keyword groups:

- 1) Sustainable construction projects,
- 2) Sustainability assessment indicators, and
- 3) Sustainability assessment frameworks and tools.

The final search string was applied to title, abstract, and keyword, yielding an initial dataset of 3,002 publications.

The dataset was refined using the following inclusion criteria: peer-reviewed journal articles, written in English, published between 2013 and 2025, and appearing in journals with at least three relevant articles. This latter condition helped reduce the high number of unrelated results, considering that many of which came from journals outside the construction field. Applying these criteria resulted in 942 peer-reviewed journal articles.

These articles were then screened using the following exclusion criteria: 1) the study is not related to sustainability assessment; 2) the focus is not on construction projects. After title and abstract screening, 246 articles met the eligibility requirements. A full-text review further refined this set, resulting in 231 articles selected for detailed analysis.

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3.1. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW PROCESS

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3.2. RESULTS OF THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

3.2.1. SCIENTOMETRIC ANALYSIS

A scientometric analysis was conducted to provide an overview of the research landscape on sustainability assessment in construction projects. This analysis examines publication trends, key publishing journals, country-level contributions, and thematic clusters based on keyword co-occurrence.

Publication trends

The annual distribution of the 231 selected articles from 2013 to early 2025 is shown in Figure 3. Between 2013 and 2017, the number of publications remained modest, ranging from 2 to 16 articles per year. From 2018 onwards, research output exhibited a steady increase, with annual publications consistently exceeding 17. A sharp rise occurred in 2022, peaking at 41 articles, the highest recorded output in the coverage period. Although there was a slight decline in 2023 (31 articles) and 2024 (32 articles), publication numbers remained significantly higher than in the earlier years. The presence of four publications in the first months of 2025 indicates continued strong interest in the field. This growth trend reflects the increasing policy and industry focus on decarbonisation, green building standards, and performance tracking in the construction sector.

Figure 1: RoundView Learning tool to provoke new thinking, used in networking at start.

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Journals' contribution

The distribution of the 231 reviewed articles across journals was examined to identify the main outlets for research on sustainability assessment in construction (Table 2). Results show that publications are concentrated in a relatively small set of journals, with Sustainability emerging as the most prolific source, contributing 35 articles (14.77% of the total). Other leading journals include Building and Environment, Sustainable Cities and Society, and Buildings.

Table 2 Top contributing journals

Journal Title	Relevant Published Articles	% Total Publication
Sustainability	35	14.77
Building and Environment	19	8.02
Sustainable Cities and Society	18	7.59
Buildings	15	6.33
Journal of Building Engineering	14	5.91
Journal of Cleaner Production	13	5.49
Energy and Buildings	11	4.64
Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	7	2.95
Journal of Green Building	6	2.53
Energies	6	2.53

Countries' analysis

The geographical distribution of research output is presented in Figure 4. Both developed and developing countries are represented. Leading contributors include China, United Kingdom, India, Australia, and United States, followed by active participants such as Italy, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Iran, Germany, Canada, Hong Kong, and Spain. The network visualisation shows strong co-authorship links—for example, between the United Kingdom and India, China and Malaysia, and Australia with both European and Asian partners—indicating substantial international collaboration.

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Figure 1: RoundView Learning tool to provoke new thinking, used in networking at start.

Keywords co-occurrence analysis

A keywords co-occurrence analysis was conducted to identify the major research themes within sustainability assessment in construction projects (Figure 5). The resulting network map reveals five distinct clusters, each representing a thematic focus area.

- Cluster 1: Sustainability Assessment Frameworks and Indicators (Red):**
 This cluster focuses on sustainability assessment frameworks, key performance indicators, and multi-criteria decision-making processes. It reflects the methodological backbone of sustainability evaluation, encompassing the development and application of structured frameworks for assessing construction projects.

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- **Cluster 2: Green Building Standards and Rating Systems (Green).** Centred on green building certification systems, assessment methods, and benchmarking tools, this theme highlights the role of rating systems, such as BREEAM and LEED, in guiding and measuring sustainable building practices.
- **Cluster 3: Smart and Intelligent Building Technologies for Sustainability Assessment (Blue).** This cluster links to intelligent building concepts, facility management, hierarchical systems, and assessment tools. It captures the integration of advanced technologies to improve monitoring, evaluation, and optimisation of sustainability performance.
- **Cluster 4: Life Cycle Assessment and Environmental Sustainability (Yellow).** Focusing on life cycle assessment (LCA), environmental impact assessment (EIA), carbon emissions, and long-term environmental footprints, this theme addresses the evaluation of a building's total sustainability impact from design to end-of-life.
- **Cluster 5: Indoor Environmental Quality Assessment (Purple).** This cluster examines indoor air quality, energy conservation and utilisation, and the relationship between building performance and occupant well-being in sustainable construction.

Figure 5:
Co-occurrence of
keywords

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3.2.2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS

This section presents the preliminary findings from the full-text analysis. At this stage, the review focuses on the scope and methodological characteristics of the studies, extracting information on thematic focus, country of study, building types, research methodology, and stated aim.

It should be emphasised that this analysis is still in progress. In subsequent stages, a more detailed examination will be undertaken in the following areas:

- **Indicators:** Specific metrics used to assess sustainability performance, including energy efficiency, carbon emissions, waste reduction, and indoor environmental quality.
- **Frameworks:** The adoption and adaptation of sustainability assessment systems such as BREEAM, LEED, CASBEE, and other regional or project-specific frameworks.
- **Lifecycle integration:** The extent to which sustainability tracking is incorporated across different stages of a construction project, from planning and design to construction, operation, and end-of-life.

Expanding the analysis in these directions will enable a more comprehensive understanding of the methods, tools, and practices applied in sustainability assessment for construction projects.

Distribution across thematic clusters

The preliminary in-depth analysis categorised all 231 reviewed articles into the five thematic clusters identified in the keyword co-occurrence analysis (Figure 6). Sustainability assessment frameworks and indicators is the most extensively covered theme, accounting for 120 articles (51.95%).

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The second most prevalent theme is green building standards and rating systems (74 articles, 32.03%), followed by life cycle assessment and environmental sustainability (20 articles, 8.66%), indoor environmental quality and energy efficiency (10 articles, 4.33%), and smart and intelligent building technologies for sustainability (7 articles, 3.03%).

Figure 6:
Number of articles
by themes

Distribution across building types

The reviewed studies address a wide range of building types (Figure 7). Residential buildings are the most frequently studied category (45 articles, 19.48%), followed by commercial buildings (26 articles, 11.26%), public service buildings (20 articles, 8.66%), and educational buildings (11 articles, 4.76%). Research on industrial buildings is limited (5 articles, 2.16%), while mixed building types account for 9 articles (3.90%) and infrastructure projects for 7 articles (3.03%). The largest share (108 articles, 46.75%) does not specify a particular building type, focusing instead on general frameworks and assessment methods.

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Figure 7: Number of articles by building types

Geographical distribution of studies

The geographical coverage of the reviewed studies shows a strong regional concentration (Figure 8). Asia leads with 84 articles (36.36%), followed by global studies (49 articles, 21.21%) and Europe (35 articles, 15.15%). Other contributions come from North America (23 articles, 9.96%), the Middle East (21 articles, 9.09%), Africa (10 articles, 4.33%), South America (7 articles, 3.03%), and Oceania (5 articles, 2.16%). The dominance of Asia and global-scale studies highlights both the regional strengths and the opportunities to expand research in underrepresented regions.

Figure 8:
Number of articles by regions

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Research gaps across thematic clusters

The preliminary in-depth analysis also identified several research gaps that cut across the five thematic clusters.

- **Gap 1 – Lack of tailored frameworks for educational buildings:** Although educational buildings are an important public sector asset, few studies develop or adapt sustainability assessment frameworks specifically for this building type, particularly within the context of universities and other higher education institutions.
- **Gap 2 – Limited research on implementation processes:** While many studies discuss certification systems such as BREEAM and LEED, there is insufficient investigation into the practical challenges, procedural steps, and organisational changes required for successful implementation in real-world projects.
- **Gap 3 – Limited discussion on how digital technologies enhance assessment effectiveness or usability:** Although smart technologies (e.g., IoT, BIM, AI) are increasingly linked to sustainability assessment, there is limited empirical evidence on how these tools improve the accuracy, efficiency, and user-friendliness of assessment processes.
- **Gap 4 – Assessment frameworks/tools prioritise environmental indicators, overlooking the social dimension:** LCA-based studies tend to focus heavily on environmental metrics such as energy, carbon, and materials, with relatively little integration of social sustainability indicators (e.g., health, equity, and community impact).

These gaps highlight the need for more context-specific frameworks, deeper exploration of implementation processes, stronger integration of digital tools, and a more balanced consideration of environmental and social dimensions in sustainability assessment.

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Figure 9: Research gaps

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3.3. SUMMARY

The SLR revealed that research on sustainability assessment in construction projects has grown rapidly in the last decade, particularly in areas relating to sustainability frameworks, green building standards, and life cycle assessment. However, the analysis also identified notable gaps:

- A lack of tailored frameworks for specific building types, particularly educational buildings.
- Limited research on implementation processes, including organisational, procedural, and operational challenges.
- Insufficient integration of digital technologies to improve assessment accuracy, usability, and efficiency.
- A strong focus on environmental indicators, with less attention to social sustainability metrics such as health, equity, and community impact.

For the University of Manchester, these findings suggest that the updated EPM PM7 tracker should:

1. Incorporate sector-specific criteria for educational buildings, drawing on relevant global best practices.
2. Integrate digital tools such as BIM, IoT-based monitoring, and data analytics to streamline data collection and improve usability.
3. Balance environmental and social indicators to reflect a more holistic understanding of sustainability.
4. Embed lifecycle-based tracking to monitor sustainability performance from early design through to building operation.

By addressing these gaps, the revised tracker will be better aligned with both current research insights and the university's long-term sustainability ambitions.

4. CO-DEVELOPMENT WORKSHOP

4.1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

On June 23, 2025, an interactive workshop was run by the Construction & Refurbishment Sub-Group of the Material Resource Management Group at The University of Manchester (UoM). The workshop aimed to evaluate and suggest improvements to the UoM sustainability tracking process for both new construction and retrofitting of buildings on campus. This is crucial as the university undergoes an ambitious programme of transforming the campus to achieve net zero carbon emissions and embed sustainability-thinking into existing and future construction projects.

The workshop was attended by 30 participants, with participants from 3 Professional Services (3), Estates (9), External contractors (7) and Academics (11).

Ketso, a hands-on toolkit for creative engagement, was used to engage the participants in dialogue and gather their ideas. The RoundView, a systems-based framework of sustainability learning and communication, was used to spark new thinking about sustainable futures as part of the dialogue.

466 ideas were developed, with a few key ideas shown in this executive summary. The full report first gives a summary of key themes to emerge, along with a summary of the subset of these ideas that were highlighted as important by the participants at the workshop.

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A spreadsheet with all ideas transcribed can be downloaded from [this link](#).

Sustainability on campus, some key ideas for the future:

- Embed circular economy principles in all projects such as design for decarbonisation
- More collaboration between departments, more interaction
- Improve culture around environmental sustainability across all students & staff
- Ownership at every level
- Build sustainability into new starter inductions
- Embed sustainability into all courses at all levels
- Provide more knowledge to staff & students on end of life of materials
- Involve sustainability consultants earlier in project planning process

Blue sky sustainability ideas for campus included:

- Regenerative design - maximising co-benefits for people + planet (and learning from nature & biomimicry)
- Put environment into every decision making process
- Foster a culture of sustainability – ways of living
- Change our behaviour e.g. cycle more, walk toward using environmentally friendly options
- Interactive workshop / activities to interest stakeholders
- Keep going with community engagement
- Upskill students to reduce consumption e.g. mending workshops for clothing + electrical items

Key characteristics and suggestions for the tracker included:

- Real time tracking
- "Single point of truth" Real time data
- Includes measures of success
- Incorporate tracking into milestones / gateway sign-off
- Ensure lessons learnt feed into future projects
- Capture results & transfer lessons to next stages or other projects
- Collect & effectively use data to predict future projects' performance
- KPIs that increase ambition as the industry progresses – not a static domain

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- A tracker needs to keep up with changing industry best practice
- Feedback from users on what materials have worked
- Feedback from building users
- Interactive + fun
- Story telling
- Need to know how our university actually use the tracker
- Benchmark it against others

Future possibilities for how we prioritise and make decisions included:

- How does the tracker react to budget constraints or design constraints?
- Holding the line on sustainable project regardless of cost
- Who makes the final decision regarding sustainability?
- What controls are in-place in our procurement and funding (RSO) process?
- Write down / report on design decisions
- Cost benefit analysis
- Prioritise key impact items
- Move away from 'target' approach?
- Tailor sustainability targets to project scope but still challenge brief
- Assess co-benefits of options
- Sustainable awareness
- Active engagement with design team on bespoke optioneering studies
- Integrating with infrastructure plan
- Lifestyle costing to guide decision making
- Incentivising sustainable projects (funds)
- Better community engagement to promote & reuse

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4.2. WORKSHOP PROCESS AND TYPES OF IDEAS DEVELOPED

There were two stages in the dialogue, first looking at sustainability on in construction on campus more broadly, then exploring tracking progress towards sustainability in construction, and how we can effectively learn from this tracking.

Following a brief introduction to the day and The University of Manchester's 2035 Strategy by Obuks Ejohwomu, participants were asked to write their ideas on different coloured leaves in response to a series of questions. For each question, participants first had the opportunity to develop ideas on their own. These ideas were then shared with the group at the table and placed on the shared Ketso workspace, forming clusters of similar ideas.

Sustainability on Campus

In the coffee and networking at the start of the workshop, and part way through the first dialogue, the participants were introduced to the RoundView framework of sustainability by Dr. Joanne Tippett.

The RoundView emerged from her research at the University of Manchester. It gives a holistic view of the root causes of all environmental problems, and their positive opposites. This serves as a navigational tool to test if plans, projects and actions are likely to move us towards sustainability, or conversely, are likely to cause unintended consequences.

After a brief introduction to the RoundView, participants were asked for further 'blue sky' ideas about sustainability on campus.

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Figure 11: Participants engaging with RoundView learning tools to encourage a holistic view

There were then a series of brief presentations:

- UoM sustainability strategy and targets, Sarah Choi
- Literature on sustainability tracking, Zheng Gong
- UoM Novel UoM Sustainable Construction guide, Andrea Carvajal (Etude)

This led into further dialogue amongst participants about tracking sustainability in construction on campus, and learning from it, with the following questions:

	<p>Grey Barriers, challenges and gaps</p>	
	<p>Yellow Solutions/ways to overcome barriers (this stage was done as a table swap, to encourage participants to solve barriers from another group)</p>	

Figure 12 Ketso leaves to capture participants' ideas

Ideas were placed around themes (branches on the Ketso) to structure the conversation.

The resulting picture of participants' thinking served to record the ideas, structure the discussion and stimulate more ideas as they went along.

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Figure 13: Ketso felt used to structure ideas emerging in dialogue

The themes used to structure the dialogue were:

- What we measure (indicators)
- How we measure (and how does it)
- How we use, and learn from, the measurement
- How we prioritise and make decisions
- Sustainability on campus

4.3. RESULTS OF THE WORKSHOP

4.3.1. SUMMARY OF IDEAS FROM WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

Sustainability on campus

There were 270 ideas in total, and 182 ideas for future possibilities for sustainability on campus. A rough draft of coding of the ideas is charted below.

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The breadth of ideas around **‘what we do well’**, encompassing landscape management for biodiversity, to retrofitting buildings and focus on internal operations such as sustainability in labs (LEAF), setting well-defined targets for scope 1-3 emissions, shows an awareness of the steps that have already been taken. This includes recognising the scale of the ambition that the University is showing. There were several ideas around how we are doing well integrating sustainability into teaching and learning, and using research to feedback on sustainability outcomes.

The theme with the largest number of ideas overall and across each type of idea was ‘Innovation, culture and communication’, with a notably high number of ideas around ‘what we do well’ (as well as the highest number of barriers and challenges). This included a comment about the value of ‘having social responsibility embedded in our core goal’.

Some key ideas for the future include:

- Embed circular economy principles in all projects such as design for decarbonisation
- More collaboration between departments, more interaction

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- Improve culture around environmental sustainability across all students & staff
- Ownership at every level
- Build sustainability into new starter inductions
- Embed sustainability into all courses at all levels
- Provide more knowledge to staff & students on end of life of materials
- Involve sustainability consultants earlier in project planning process

Blue sky sustainability ideas included:

- Regenerative design - maximising co-benefits for people + planet (and learning from nature & biomimicry)
- Put environment into every decision making process
- Foster a culture of sustainability – ways of living
- Change our behaviour e.g. cycle more, walk toward using environmentally friendly options
- Interactive workshop / activities to interest stakeholders
- Keep going with community engagement
- Upskill students to reduce consumption e.g. mending workshops for clothing + electrical items
- Complete move from capitalist consumer model - less things

The theme with the next most discussion as well as the highest proportion of ideas to be added after considering the RoundView, was 'Materials and circularity'. Before considering the RoundView, there was already discussion about the circular economy and the need to 'design for disassembly and implement circularity including in construction', with some specific recommendations: a 'larger furniture store' and to 'invest in more sustainable lab equipment'.

Further ideas to emerge as blue sky thinking under this theme were:

- Infrastructure = no virgin materials only re-use (and / or natural materials) for buildings
- Retrofit + refurb
- Research into material banks that help reduce use of new ones
- Reuse more recycle most incinerate - almost never
- Product as a service
- Extending product lifespan

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- On site chemical cleaning
- Recycle as many as possible. Consider end-of life / demolition in building
- Closed loop system on campus e.g. material reuse, growing food, no food waste
- Apply circular economy principles on everything purchased - zero general waste
- Recycle on-site (e.g. food waste)

There was also a high proportion of blue sky thinking under 'Renewable energy', 'Transport and movement' and 'Biodiversity and wildlife', perhaps reflecting the brief period to pause and consider a holistic approach to sustainability, which helped stretch participants' thinking to a more holistic approach.

One participant reflected in feedback after the event:

"I really appreciated the chance to step back and reflect on sustainability from a broader perspective and consider the long-term impacts. It's rare, especially when working within a specific niche, to take the time to connect with the bigger picture. I thought it was great that even in a room full of sustainability professionals, it [the RoundView] still prompted fresh thinking and meaningful discussion." Member of Construction Management Group.

There was a high level of discussion around generating renewable energy on campus, 'embrace renewable energy' (no fossil fuels, maximise renewables, centralise), the need to 'encourage walking & cycling by making the campus safe', and several ideas around restoring ecosystems: 'green roofs/walls' and more broadly, 'green + blue infrastructure on campus and old buildings'.

There was also a lot of discussion around food, bridging the discussions of biodiversity and circularity, with ideas including:

- Community growing garden. Reduce food waste
- Regreen campus with managed landscape use for fuel + products
- Food Recycle System - where are they going
- All cafes to sell vegan food

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There were also comments around the need to think of the campus in the wider perspective, 'prioritising co-ordinated civil infrastructure over individual building projects' and asking if we 'can we go beyond catering for just UOM estate? e.g. flood risk mitigation for the wider area'.

Figure 8: Number of articles by regions

4.3.2. TRACKING PROGRESS TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY ON CAMPUS AND LEARNING

The following chart shows the distribution of types of ideas according to the themes that were used to structure the in-depth discussion around sustainability tracking following the presentations.

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Figure 15: Chart reflecting the types of ideas to emerge, structured by participants against themes

The branch that gathered the greatest number of ideas was ‘How we prioritise and make decisions’, with a particularly high number of ideas for both future possibilities as well as barriers and challenges. The relatively high number of ideas around barriers to ‘Sustainability on campus’ could be explained by the fact that there was a good deal of creative discussion around this topic in the first round of dialogue, producing 72 ideas around ‘what we do well’, 90 ‘future possibilities’ and 86 ‘blue sky sustainability possibilities’.

The following section shows clusters of ideas that were identified as a priority or highlighted as important/interesting by the participants during the workshop. This starts with overarching barriers and solutions, and is followed by a summary of organised by the themes given on the Ketso felts to structure the discussion. Ideas highlighted by participants are shown in bold.

Note that the ideas for sustainability on campus that emerged in the second stage of dialogue are synthesised in the discussion above.

A few key barriers, and solutions to them that were seen as overarching are shown below:

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Barrier / challenge / gap	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioural change - resistance to it • Culture - end user problems • People understanding of what to track & when to track • People's understanding of what sustainable is 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education of empowered leaders • Policy change, priority & financial support • 1. Co-creation at start • 2. Dialogue with end users • 3. Capturing lessons learned
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lots of management not a lot of leadership • Leadership that truly think / acts sustainably 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empower people to act as leaders • Specialised empowered roles • Education of empowered leaders • Policy change, priority & financial support
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government policy confidence • Legislation (i.e. building regulations) • Planning advisory! And other authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use our expertise to influence policies

What we measure (indicators)

Same metrics across projects

- Adopt universal metrics & central systems for uniformity / comparison
- Targets bespoke & generic
- Baseline where we are with our estate
- How we compare ourselves to other HEI
- Feedback – impact internal + external

Energy consumption in use

- Figures for construction waste + recycling
- Energy, embodied carbon, thermal comfort, biodiversity
- Materials passports

Tracking end-users' well-being

- Tracking sustainability in relation to safety and health

How we measure (and who does it)

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Barrier / challenge / gap	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment and buy in-attitudes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consequences carrot + stick • Incentive to get all people involved
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of consequences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No oversight across different projects • UoM to create validation / liability process (for targets not met) • Regular feedback (report) from projects / construction / operation teams
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vague concepts both academic / industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define indicators + metrics • Define roles + responsibilities • Tracking + development • Avoid generalisations "implement circularity"

Further key concepts that were highlighted were:

- Transparency
- Find meaningful things to track rather than many
- Digital driven measurement system

How we use, and learn from the measurement

Barrier / challenge / gap	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate knowledge and understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All relevant staff have appropriate training on metrics + CPD • Education from early age • Community • Build into master's programme • New effecting teaching methods • Keep learning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No ownership at each level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Let stakeholders be responsible for involvement in the tracking processes Appointment of fuel lead?

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Key characteristics and suggestions for the tracker included:

- Real time tracking
- "Single point of truth" Real time data
- Includes measures of success
- Incorporate tracking into milestones / gateway sign-off
- Ensure lessons learnt feed into future projects
- Capture results & transfer lessons to next stages or other projects
- Collect & effectively use data to predict future projects' performance
- KPIs that increase ambition as the industry progresses – not a static domain
- A tracker needs to keep up with changing industry best practice
- Feedback from users on what materials have worked
- Feedback from building users
- Interactive + fun
- Story telling
- Need to know how our university actually use the tracker
- Benchmark it against others

How we prioritise and make decisions

The following table shows linked barriers and solutions that were highlighted by participants as key.

Barrier / challenge / gap	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder complexity issues • Numerous stake holders involved (barriers in communication & agendas may differ) • Mindset - getting people along • Stakeholder buy-in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage the right people from the very early stage of the project
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enough staff to put procedures into practise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify who is responsible - key individuals Incentive the process to encourage staff to take them on • To align PHD / dissertations to the actual projects (use student resource)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People working in silos - lack of collaborative thinking / collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data integration to solve silo working • Communications / guidelines / regular meetups • Question the proposed solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of data integration to support better decision-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open data - well communicated • Agreed process to incorporate ESAs from very beginning of project

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Clusters of future possibilities around how we prioritise and make decisions:

How does the tracker react to budget constraints or design constraints?

- Holding the line on sustainable project regardless of cost
- Who makes the final decision regarding sustainability?
- What controls are in-place in our procurement and funding (RSO) process?
- Write down / report on design decisions

- **Cost benefit analysis**
- Prioritise key impact items
- Move away from 'target' approach?
- Tailor sustainability targets to project scope but still challenge brief
- Assess co-benefits of options

- **Sustainable awareness**
- Active engagement with design team on bespoke optioneering studies
- **Integrating with infrastructure plan**
- **Lifestyle costing to guide decision making**
- Incentivising sustainable projects (funds)
- Better community engagement to promote & reuse

4.3.3 CODING THE WORKSHOP DATA: FROM THEMES TO CONCEPTS

To gain a deeper understanding of the patterns and nuances within the workshop responses, a coding process was undertaken to categorise individual responses into more specific conceptual categories within each theme. Rather than relying on pre-defined categories, the coding was conducted inductively through close reading and iterative comparison across the dataset, allowing key concepts to emerge organically. Each response was reviewed and assigned to a category based on its primary focus. Figures 16 to 20 show the coding results, in which the blue-shaded boxes represent participants' responses to the question "What do we need for sustainability tracking?" and orange boxes represent barriers identified in response to the question "What are the barriers?". Red Text within the orange boxes indicates the most critical barriers highlighted by participants.

Figure 16: Theme 1 – What we measure

Figure 17: Theme 2 – How we measure

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Figure 18: Theme 3 – How we use and learn from the measurement

Figure 19: Theme 4 – How we prioritise and make decision

Figure 20 Theme 5 – Sustainability practices on campus

4.4. SUMMARY

There was a great deal of in-depth discussion in this workshop from a range of participants covering multiple disciplines and areas of the University. In feedback after the event, one participant commented: “The workshop facilitated engagement and participation. With Ketso, everybody had a voice, if you were at the table, your voice was captured with the leaves”.

The ideas presented in this report provide an overview of the ideas generated. The accompanying spreadsheet gives a larger set of results, acting as resource for further strategic planning. This will help the University of Manchester shift from environmental degradation, unintended consequences that stated from the Industrial Revolution to becoming a key driver in the next phase of inventing and creating a sustainable, and regenerative future.

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